

Overview

The aim is to conduct an impartial comparison between numerous models which have been developed to examine land-atmosphere exchanges within the urban environment.

The project commenced with participants being issued a test dataset (VL92) which they have run and returned their output (Table 1 details the planned timetable for the project and Table 2 details current participants). This was to ensure that all parties can “communicate” and for preparation for later stages. We currently have approximately 35 modelling groups participating.

Initial results from the first round of this work (which will consist of four stages) will be available for presentation at the AMS Annual Meeting in January 2009 which has an urban theme. Depending on interest, we may want to consider a session at this meeting. Abstracts are due August 1st. Later we will ask you if you would be interested in participating in such a session. It is hoped that the presentation of results for Round 1 will be made at the IAUC 7 Meeting in June 2009.

Current Status: ALPHA (Stage 1)

This month is the start of Stage 1 (see Table 1). As part of this phase participants are provided with a dataset which consists of forcing data only. The dataset is referred to as **ALPHA**. In this first stage participants are required to run their models **offline** using only this data and making any assumptions necessary to use their models. The precise location from which this data were obtained is not provided. The data were collected at the local scale within a city.

Once the ALPHA dataset is run, participants are required to return the output data and details of the parameter values used. Until such outputs are received, further sets of data will not be released for the subsequent stages. The timetable is given in Table 1.

Subject to returning satisfactory data participants will be issued with data for Stage 2 from 1 May. This will consist of some parameter information. The same forcing data will be used.

For further detailed information please see the ALPHA FAQs at the end of this newsletter. Please refer to March 2008 newsletter for VL92 FAQ. If these documents fail to answer any queries you may have then please contact us at the email address: UrbanMet@kcl.ac.uk.

Table 1: Planned timetable

Target date	Objective	Status
1 Mar	Outputs of test data returned	Complete
1 April	First dataset released (Stage 1)	Current
30 April	Deadline for return of output	On-target
1 May	Second dataset released*	On-target
1 June	Third dataset released*	On-target
1 July	Fourth dataset released*	On target

* Note: subsequent datasets will only be released following receipt of output from the previous step.

General FAQs

What is this project about and where can I find updates?

Please see the documents at:

www.kcl.ac.uk/ip/suegrimmond/model_comparison.htm

What are the first steps required to join the model comparison?

If you would like to participate then please contact us at:

UrbanMet@kcl.ac.uk

I need more information about the VL92 dataset

See the March 2008 newsletter.

What do the model codes stand for?

Participants have been asked to name their models (usually an acronym). When the results are presented anonymous codes will be used – you will only know your code. Models will be referred to by this anonymous code when inter-comparisons are being conducted and results published.

Will there be a second or third round?

It is hoped that there will be a second and potentially a third round of comparison, each using a different set of forcing data. This of course, depends on data availability and on the success of the first round. It is important to realise that success of this project depends on the commitment of all participants and their meeting the deadlines.

Will I be told of the performance of my model?

Yes – individual groups will be informed but only on the status of their particular model(s). Overall results will be published but models will be referred to by a code known only to that participant and the project coordinators.

I have queries specific to Round 1/ALPHA.

Please refer to the ALPHA data FAQs which can be found at the end of this newsletter.

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Table 2: Participating modelling groups and their current status

<i>Model</i>	<i>Participant(s)</i>	<i>Received Contact?</i>	<i>Test data output received at KCL</i>	<i>Output satisfactory?</i>	<i>First dataset released?</i>
<i>BEP02</i>	Martilli	✓	✓	✓	✓
<i>BEP_BEM08</i>	Francisco	✓	✓	✓	✓
<i>CLMU</i>	Oleson	✓	✓	✓	✓
<i>ENVImet</i>	Bruse	✓			
<i>GCTTC</i>	Shashua Bar	✓			
<i>HIRLAM-U</i>	Baklanov	✓†			
<i>HPDM-Urban</i>	Hanna	✓†			
<i>LUMPS</i>	Loridan	✓	✓	✓	✓
<i>MM5u</i>	Dandou; Tombrou	✓	✓	✓	✓
<i>JULESK</i>	Gouvea	✓	✓	✓	✓
<i>JULES1T</i>	Best	✓	✓	✓	✓
<i>JULES2T</i>	Best	✓	✓	✓	✓
<i>JULES-U</i>	Porson	✓	✓	✓	✓
<i>MUCM</i>	Kondo	✓	✓	✓	✓
<i>MUKLIMO</i>	Sievers	†			
<i>NJU-UCM-S</i>	Zhang	✓			
<i>NJU-UCM-M</i>	Zhang	✓			
<i>NSLUCM</i>	Miao; Chen	✓	✓	✓	✓
<i>NSLUCMK</i>	Loridan	✓	✓	✓	✓
<i>RUM2</i>	Bohnenstengel	✓	✓	✓	✓
<i>RUM4</i>	Bohnenstengel	✓	✓	✓	✓
<i>SEB</i>	Pearlmutter	✓			
<i>SESPUM6.1</i>	Chemel	✓			
<i>SLUCM</i>	Kusaka	✓			
<i>SM2U</i>	Calmet	✓	✓	✓	✓
<i>SUEB</i>	Fortuniak	✓	✓	✓	✓
<i>SUMM</i>	Kanda				
<i>SUNBEEM</i>	Arnfield	✓			
<i>TEB</i>	Pigeon; Masson	✓	✓	✓	✓
<i>TEB</i>	Mailhot	✓†			
<i>TEB07</i>	Hamdi	✓	✓	✓	✓
<i>TUF2D</i>	Krayenhoff; Voogt	✓			
<i>TUF3D</i>	Krayenhoff; Voogt	✓	✓	✓	✓
<i>UCLM</i>	Mills				
<i>VUCM</i>	Lee; Baik	✓	✓	✓	✓
-	Taha	✓†			
-	Brown	✓			

† unable to participate in first round.

This project contributes to:

Urban Model Comparison ALPHA Data FAQs

Where can I get the ALPHA data from?

If you are a confirmed participant, the evaluation data will be sent to you in either (or both) and ASCII or netCDF format. The file containing the data is called ALPHA. If you have not received the data or if you would like it to be resent, please contact us at:

UrbanMet@kcl.ac.uk

I cannot read the dataset

If this happens it may be that you are examining either the netCDF or ASCII file believing it to be the other. If you are still unable to view the data then please email and we will endeavour to help you.

What does the ALPHA dataset consist of?

At Stage 1, the content of the forcing data only set consists of the following variables:

- Year – the year of the data (either 1 or 2)
- DecTime - decimal time
- Day – day of year in format 1-365
- Time – hour of day in 24-hour format
- SWdown – incoming shortwave radiation ($W m^{-2}$)
- LWdown – downwelling longwave radiation ($W m^{-2}$)
- Wind_N – northward, v, wind component ($m s^{-1}$)
- Wind_E – eastward, u, wind component ($m s^{-1}$)
- PSurf – station pressure (Pa)
- Tair – air temperature (K)
- Qair – specific humidity ($kg kg^{-1}$)
- Rainf – rainfall rate ($kg m^{-2} s^{-1}$)

Where possible, these variables meet the ALMA convention in terms of naming and units, although where this has not been possible, new naming conventions have been adopted.

What is the ALMA convention?

This was developed to facilitate exchange of forcing data for land-surface schemes and their results (ALMA stands for Assistance for Land-surface Modelling Activities). For further information please see:

<http://www.lmd.jussieu.fr/~polcher/ALMA/>

Should all variables in the test data be used?

Not necessarily – if your model does not need all the data then do not use it.

Should the whole timeseries of data be used? Yes.

What are averaging periods for the data?

The data are half-hourly averaged values for the time ending i.e. 10:30 is 10:01 to 10:30. Your data should be half-hourly averaged for this time period and should not be a sample/instantaneous value on the half-hour.

What time-zone should be assumed?

Please use the time within the test file (i.e. local time).

I need latitude and longitude

If you need these details then please assume the following location: 37.7308 °S, 65.014 °W

Does the ALPHA dataset contain filled gaps?

Yes it does. Details of the gaps filled and methods used to complete it can be found within the ALPHA file.

Are there any data available for model “spin up”?

If you need this we will assume the first ~100 days of data are spin up (they will be analysed separately). However, you must still provide the output for all time periods.

I do not need “spin-up” data.

In this case, please simply use the whole ALPHA dataset with your model.

What are the temporal and spatial scales to be modelled?

Spatial: the model output should be for a point that is at the equivalent of the first layer in a meso-scale model or at the blending height. i.e. it is local scale (spatially integrated for a neighbourhood) as are the observations. It should not be a microscale result for a point within the canyon.

The forcing data and the observations which the models, will be compared to, were taken at:

6.25 x mean roughness height

Temporal: The model results will be compared on a 30-minute time scale (and longer). These will be the average for the 30-minute period and are for the half-hourly ending time stamp.

What values should I used as parameters for my model?

At this stage in the project no parameter values will be given to you. Where these are required you are to make “sensible assumptions” based on the fact that the data were obtained from within a city. If you feel this is not possible please contact us to discuss.

What more can we know about the ALPHA data?

At this stage we can tell you no more about the site at which this data were collected. If you require details of any other parameters you will need to assume these.

What data should I return?

- 1) Model results for the full 474.4167 days of data (see Table 2 for more details of precise data we need returned)
- 2) Parameter values used/assumed
- 3) Spin up procedure (if applicable)
- 4) Height which model results are for
- 5) Metadata which explains you model results (column labels, definition, units)

What results do I need to return?

Table 3 list the minimum output variables that we need returned, along with the associated name and units according to the ALMA convention:

Table 3 Minimum data to be returned

<i>Variable</i>	<i>ALMA Name</i>	<i>ALMA Units</i>
<i>Upwelling short-wave radiation</i>	SWup	W m ⁻²
<i>Upwelling long-wave radiation</i>	LWup	W m ⁻²
<i>Net all-wave radiation</i>	Qnet	W m ⁻²
<i>Sensible heat flux</i>	Qh	W m ⁻²
<i>Latent heat flux</i>	Qle	W m ⁻²
<i>Storage heat flux</i>	Qstor	W m ⁻²
<i>Momentum flux[†]</i>	Qtau	N m ⁻²
<i>Anthropogenic heat flux[†]</i>	Qanth	W m ⁻²

* where there is no ALMA convention, please use this naming and unit convention.

† optional variables – if your model does not output this data then you do not need to return these values.

In what format should the model outputs be returned?

1. We will accept data in ASCII format or netCDF files. Please ensure the format of your data matches that which you returned to us in the test phase. If the format will differ then please let us know prior to returning it.
2. When submitting your output please include a metadata file with the format of your data and the units used.
3. We need to know the parameter values you chose. (We will provide more details shortly about how to return this)
4. Ideally your output file will be formatted in the same way as the ALPHA netCDF or ASCII file and will use ALMA conventions (or our specific conventions).

Do I need to tell you what parameters I have used in implementing my model?

Yes – this is important, please return these when you return your model data.

What constitutes satisfactory data?

This means that we are able to access and analyse the data and that the other details requested are provided. Also, that the data returned to us should meet the ALMA conventions as closely as possible.

What stages does the project consist of?

The project will consist of four stages. The data that will be provided at each stage are:

- Stage 1 (current) – only forcing variables
- Stage 2 – some urban parameters values
- Stage 3 – more parameter values
- Stage 4 – evaluation dataset

What is the timetable of the whole project?

We would like the output of your models to be returned to us as soon as possible and within a month ideally, this will complete Stage 1. Table 3 shows a timetable of the project.

Table 4 Timetable of project

<i>Data Set</i>	<i>Round</i>	<i>Stage</i>	<i>Comments</i>
VL92	0	0	Complete
ALPHA	1	1	Data distributed 1 April
		1	Output returned 30 April
		2	Data distributed 1 May
		3	Data distributed 1 June
		4	Data distributed 1 July

Will I automatically receive the data for each stage?

No – you will only receive data for the following stage when you return the output from the previous stage to us and we find it to be acceptable.

Can I distribute the data I am sent (either the VL92 data or the evaluation data) or use it for another purpose?

No – the data we send you is for use by you on this project only. We ask you to agree to this by participating in this work. Any data we send must also not be exchanged among participants as you may be at a different stage in the project.

What if I have more questions?

Please email UrbanMet@kcl.ac.uk with any further queries and we will respond as quickly as possible.

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